

**I-GREEN INITIATE:
INTEGRATION AMONG THE GOVERNMENT, THE PRIVATE
SECTORS, AND THE SOCIETY TO IMPLEMENT GREEN ECONOMY
TOWARD SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT**

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ABSTRACT

The issue of the changing environment has become a hot topic discussed today, not only in term of how much environmental damage can be reduced but also what strategy to do to keep the environment as one means of achieving sustainable development. Given the environmental problems are global problems, each country should participate in the efforts to develop a concrete solution to the environmental problems, each country as a part of the global community must also be able to contribute to creating a green economy. This paper will describe the opportunities and challenges of integration between the government, the private sector, and the society to create a green economy called I-Green Initiate. The main objectives of the Green Economy is to change the brown environment to become green environment through the integration of the three stakeholders.

First, the government as policy maker can provide incentives to private and public policies that support the green economy. In addition the government needs to invest in Research and Development (RnD) to examine how to effectively follow-up of what can be done in order to make every country become a green country like Japan, for example. Finally, the government needs to make the green economy as a national policy.

Second, the private sector must be able to implement green business by creating green products and implement a green jobs. Currently the private sector in some countries has started to take into their attention in environmental issues. Although

their core business is not directly related to environmental issues, they are willing to conduct CSR related to environmental issues. By doing this, it is expected that consumers will not only give them more respect but also buy more of their products.

Third, as people or society are often the victims of environmental, the society can be a driving force for the government and the private sector to provide green products. When the consumers prefer to use green products through green consumption, it will be a pressure for both the government and the private sector to produce green products and to implement green business.

Integration between the three stakeholders are expected to make every country realize the importance of act together to implement I-Green Initiate toward sustainable development.

Keywords : I-Green Initiate, Green Economy, Sustainable Development.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the beginning 21th century, world is facing global environmental problems, such as global climate change, the depletion of the ozone layer, desertification, deforestation, the loss of the planet’s biological diversity and the Trans boundary movements of hazardous wastes and chemicals are all environmental problems that touch every nation and adversely affect the lives and health of their populations. All of these problems are caused by economic activities that exploit natural resources such as agriculture, forest and fish resources in the sea, the use of fossil energy (oil, coal and natural gas), waste disposal, emissions of greenhouse gases, the conversion of natural ecosystems industrial, residential, infrastructure and other excessively in the past three decades. Emission of carbon dioxide is spreading across the world creating pollution and triggering global warming. The following graphic is showing the high number of carbon dioxide emission polluted our world:

Picture 1. Emission of Carbon Dioxide

Source: UNEP 2012

Moreover all of these environmental problem will have long term effects on people and societies and are either difficult or impossible to reverse over the period of one generation. Unless effective global actions are taken early, we will end up plundering our children's heritage and future in an unprecedented way. Implementation green economy action can overcome this problem but it must have collaboration between government, private, and society to raise big impacts.

Implementation of green economy in addition to reducing environmental damage and can also reduce poverty in a country. However, this must be supported by policies and strong cooperation between government, private, and society. Government's role in minimizing the bureaucracy to facilitate green investment, restore law and regulations that conflict with each other, as well as financial support. Significant contributions by a strong and competitive private sector are necessary to successfully address the double challenge of reducing poverty as well as mitigation environmental degradation and the impact of climate change. For a successful transformation to a green economy, the private sector must develop green products, services and technologies which reduce the risks of climate change and environmental degradation while intensifying efforts for adaptation to climate change. At the same time, it must increase income opportunities for the poor. Society has grown to keep environmental awareness, for example, through extension of the government. The purpose of this paper is to introduce the green economy as one solution to address the environmental damage caused by the prolonged economic activity. Through the application of the green economy is expected to maintain the natural balance and improve the country's economy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Green Economy

A green economy is about a different way of doing things. It is about recognising that our economies need to be guided by different goals, they need to be sustained by different activities, and they need to deliver different results (UNEP 2008).

Green Economy has been the most up dated way to obtain economic and environment development. United Nations Environment Program had launched the Green Economy Initiative to develop a working definition of a green economy as one that results in improved human well-being and social equity, while significantly reducing environmental risk and ecological scarcities. In other word, a green economy can be simply expressed as something which is low carbon, resource efficient, and socially inclusive.

Green economy also explained about practical implementation for public and private investment that reduce carbon emissions and pollution, enhance energy and resource efficiency, and prevent the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services in growing its income and employment. The following graphic showing some implementation in countries whose invest their capital in green growth.

Picture 2. World Average Biocapacity per Capita

Source: UNEP 2010

This concept characterized by substantially increasing investment in economic sectors that build and enhance the earth's natural capital or reduce ecological scarcities and environmental risk. There are some sectors including renewable energy, low-carbon transport, energy efficient buildings, clean technologies, improved waste management, improved freshwater provision, sustainable agriculture and forest management, and sustainable fisheries.

2.2 Government Sector

Role Government in green economy is using a range of policy tools to support the transition, including: promotion of international action; regulation; financial incentives; voluntary agreements; fiscal measures; public sector procurement; provision of information; and targeted work to unblock non-financial barriers to the deployment of clean energy technologies .Using these tools in the right way that balances supporting good behaviour and discouraging poor environmental outcomes is important for ensuring that change happens, that benefits from that change are maximized and costs are minimized. This Government is putting in place the necessary mechanisms to attract investment in the infrastructure that will support economy now and enable it to grow sustainably for our future. This includes driving investment through:

1. Supporting low carbon transport infrastructure and facilitating the development and manufacture of ultra low emission vehicles and recharging infrastructure.
2. The Green Deal which will create the financing mechanism to support investment in energy in our homes and businesses
3. Green Investment Bank which will facilitate increased and accelerated private sector investment in infrastructure projects that support economic growth and environmental objectives, such as offshore wind, industrial energy efficiency and commercial and industrial waste as well as growth capital for innovative green technologies.
4. Fiscal measures, such as environmental taxes, can be effective in driving change. They can, for example, work to discourage damaging environmental behaviours (e.g. Climate Change Levy, Landfill tax,

carbon floor price); incentivise environmentally-friendly products (e.g. Vehicle Excise Duty) and energy efficiency (e.g. Climate Change Agreements; Enhanced Capital Allowances).

5. Government has an important role helping provide information to businesses – for example, on the expected impacts of climate change, resource efficiency and resource risks. Government will continue to make information available to businesses in these areas, to make that information easier for businesses to use, and to advise businesses on how best to use it.
6. The Government is committed to supporting particularly those businesses that will be hardest hit by the transitional costs of greening the economy. Government will announce a package of measures to help

National and policy reforms play such an important role in supporting green economy inside a country. It will influence the development of international policy and market infrastructure. These investments and policy reforms provide the mechanisms and the financing for the reconfiguration of businesses, infrastructure and institutions, the adoption of sustainable consumption and production processes. Reconfiguration will lead to a higher share of green sectors contributing to GDP, greener jobs, lower energy and resource-intensive production, lower waste and pollution, and significantly lower greenhouse gas emissions. This implementation also be able to assist in the reduction of persistent poverty through targeted wealth transfers, new employment, as well as improvements in access and the flow of ecosystem goods and services to the bottom of the economic pyramid.

2.3 Private Sector

Private sector plays such an important role in implementing the green economy concept. According to EMC Case Study Sustainable Report, there are three components known in influencing the sustainability addresses including:

1. Competitors

It will be driven by innovation, meeting stakeholder expectation, and creating clear differentiation.

2. Customers

This sector acts as the pressure for meeting and delivering against sustainability issues transcends the supply chain, sustainability meets, customer expectation and improves service delivery.

3. Company.

Sustainability will be achieved by reducing costs, improving team cohesion, talent attraction and driving innovation by removing the barriers to strategy implementation.

Integration of these three components will create a long term vision toward sustainable development based on green economy.

Green business model is a model including the blending between the environment and business model (Axel Sommer, 2012). The following graphic gives big picture on how the green business differentiate with general business concept.

Picture 3. Green Business Model

Source: Managing Green Business Model Transformations, Axel Sommer 2012

2.4 Green Consumption

Based on study committed by Government of China published in the official site toward green economy, Green Consumption covers a full range of activities in both production and consumption fields, including green products, the recycling of materials, the efficient use of energy, the protection of the environment, and the preservation of species (www.china.org.cn).

This green consumption concept create new concept of green product. Green products are typically durable, non toxic, made of recycled materials, or minimally packaged. Of course, there are no completely green products, for they all use up energy and resources and create by-products and emissions during their manufacture, transport to warehouses and stores, usage, and eventual disposal. So green is relative, describing product with less impact on the environment than their alternatives (Charles Julien, 2010).

These green products are strongly connected with the environmental protection. There are 6 parts connecting in environmental protection related to green consumption such as reduce, reevaluate, reuse, recycle, and rescue. Green consumption is a principle with three implications. This principle encourages people to choose green products that are unpolluted or good for public health, wastes are to be treated under special surveillance to avoid pollution, and public understanding of consumption is to be changed so as to raise people's awareness of a healthy lifestyle, environmental protection, and energy conservation in their pursuit of a comfortable life. The ultimate goal is to achieve sustainable consumption in the country in order to balance environment and life.

Green consumption also associates with environment issues in which people engage have meaning for them and also involve material goods of some form or other, despite the fact that such practices are rarely labeled 'consumer practices' (Warde, 2005). This theory also describe that the idea that consumption itself is not a practice, rather, a moment in almost every practice – 'items consumed are put to use in the course of engaging in particular practices' (p. 145). In terms of environmental considerations, particular objects and ways of living

with the material world are not just about the production and reproduction of the everyday lives of those involved or interested in environmentalism (Horton, 2003).

2.5 Sustainable Environment

According to World Bank Group, sustainable development can be achieved by working together with policy makers, civil society, and the private sector to address climate change and encourage inclusive green growth. The following graphic provides big picture on how sustainable development are achieved by integration among economic sustainability, environmental sustainability and social sustainability.

Picture 4. Sustainable Development

Source: World Bank Group 2010

Careful case-by-case analysis will be provided to find optimal strategies, but there is considerable evidence that near-term costs can be minimized through the use of well-designed regulations and market-based policy instruments that promote least-cost ways of protecting the environment. Green growth with the integration of these three aspects can provide a pathway to more sustainable development that reconciles the urgent need for sustained growth with the

imperative of avoiding lock-in to unsustainable growth patterns and irreversible environmental damages. Green growth is not anti-growth; rather, it represents a change in how we manage economies to reflect a broader conception of what constitutes effective and sustainable growth.

3. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Benchmarking to Country Implementation

Initiating Green Initiative will require some learning from other countries which have been implementing the idea of integration among government, private sector, and society to do the green economy activities oriented. These benchmarking cases will become a foundation to create a model to learn on how the initiative is able to lead today's lifestyle toward sustainable development.

3.1.1 India

India comes up as a good example of why the advancement and expansion of sustainable energy options makes sense in a developing country context, both in environmental but also in economic and energy security terms, and why the enabling potentials of the private financial services sector must be unleashed through a suite of targeted and well-orchestrated policies. This country tried to trigger its private sector to do some development on green activities inside the business. India also invests in research and development as a purpose to create sustainable energy learning discipline. According to REN21, India succeeded to be the second leader after China among developing countries in initiating a series of sustainable energy disciplines in installing wind power and renewable capacities by the end of 2008.

3.1.2 Indonesia

The increasing of gas emissions in developing countries push some of these countries to initiate new reforms. Specific policies include reforms of subsidies for electricity industries to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, reforms of fuel subsidies making them more targeted, and other subsidies. This policy implemented in order to become a new policy instrument for the promotion of

renewable energy such as geothermal and other clean energies, as well as incentives for industries which promote environmental friendly products. These policies implemented including the incentive and integration for private sector in this case industry and society in subsidizing the creation of green products. Indonesia also has voluntarily committed to reducing greenhouse gas emissions or carbon intensity per unit of GDP by 2020 as one of its contribution to save the environment. As planned, Indonesia is committed to reducing its greenhouse gas emissions by 26%, and up to 41% with international support, by 2020. Additionally, Indonesian government also makes some initiatives such as Indonesia Climate Change Sectoral Roadmap with the objective to mainstream climate change in the Indonesian national mid-term development plan.

As the part of government contribution, Indonesia signed the Manila Declaration on Green Industry in the framework of an international conference held in the Philippines in September 2009 along more than 20 signatories from Asian countries. This agreement shows the determination to establish policies and regulatory and institutional frameworks that are favourable to a shift towards resourceefficient and low-carbon industries. The purpose of this declaration is to encourage an intensified transfer of cleaner production technologies and promotes an increased use of renewable energy, among others.

3.2 I-Green Initiate : Integration among government, private sector, and society

As the environment is the global problem, this I-Green initiate comes up with the solution to create every single solution based on the integration among government, private sector, and society. The following model helps to elaborate the integration:

Picture 5. I-Green Initiate

Source: Writer

3.2.1 Government: Regulation

An urgency comes up for the government in transforming the orientation for the regulation purpose to the green oriented. Government has such power to control over what action that the private sector take in running their business process. The negative externalities that destroying the nature most of the amount are coming from the private sector. Both national and international governmental including organization and non-organizational organization work together to form the high commitment and incentive for private to reduce the pollution created form their business process. For example, more than 700 institutional investors representing in excess of \$20 trillion in assets, and who back the UN Principles of Responsible Investment (PRI) have been committed to responsible investment (Green Economy Briefing paper, 2010). This reality indicates strong signal for the direction of capital towards low-carbon and resource-efficient activities of the future.

The government plays such an important role to create the “soft-enabling” environment in implementing green economy. Regulation settled by the government becomes the most spotlighted item to provide the incentive for green business in making the green product. Regulation such as the tax holiday,

additional facilities, and supported infrastructure will support the industry to do more green activities in their process.

Besides providing additional facilities for company with green vision, investing in research and development to find new solution for green activity will influence the process of a business process. The pollution created or the energy used will be minimized with the technology based on green vision.

3.2.2 Private Sector: Green Business

Analyzing the private sector as the main part in pushing the economic growth, private sector should contribute more in saving this nature. Looking at the ironic condition of our nature that has been explained above, the private sector should act more to preserve the environment. There are a lot of activities that can be done by the companies to be the green business. Implementing green job means putting the green identity for the company. The following diagram explains the indicators about the green job.

Picture 6. Green and Decent Jobs? A Schematic Overview

Source: UNEP 2008

This green jobs strategy implementation will put green vision in every single step that the employee do for the company. It also creates competitive advantage for this company in preserving the environment while at the same time creating profit from economic process. It also protects the company from random environmental projects creating a sustained process with intended actions, clear outcomes, and business benefits.

The green vision implementation will transcend the duality of environmental concerns and making money. This green business concept earn the organization triple bottom line reporting including economic, environmental and social. The real matter lies in using considered environmental metrics with a commitment to work in a three dimensional way. Sustainability and overall corporate strategy should be linked together as the effort in making green vision to be the bottom line of organization business process. At the end of the day, it will earn sustainability.

3.3.3 Society: Green Consumption

The urgency happening in this world is the increasing number of population. The problem is more growth means more consumption and more production, more pollution, more environmental degradation, more ruined livelihoods, more inequality and disparity. There must be a solution to press this consumption while also preserve the nature. Green consumption come up as one of the solutions to get double impact to fulfill human needs and save the environment.

Green consumption try to offer the green product as the society part of I-Green initiate. Positioning the green product will be more beneficial to be consumed is the main purpose of this initiate. Society as the main driver of company in creating its products should be integrated in this model. With the green consumption mind, society is linked together to consume green product enable the business do transition toward green business. It is not impossible to offer new concept of green product in fulfilling human needs. The data below shows that the demand for green product is increasing.

Picture 7. Global Trade in Organic Food and Drinks (1999-2009)

Source: Trade opportunities in a green economy, 2008

The additional information also support that green consumption will be successfully implemented such as there are 200 Chinese enterprises, 40 sectors, and 500 products have passed the environmental labeling certification. These factories are producing products that are closely related to people's daily necessities. Some of the products including ecological textiles, soft drinks, paper tableware, refrigerators, color TVs, computers, microwave ovens, air-conditioners, detergents, dry batteries, manmade floorboards, paints, pesticides, toilet paper, energy-saving lights, children's toys, and motor bicycles (Trade opportunities in a green economy, 2008)

The blending of the concept and facts are crucially supported in implementing the green consumption by society as the part of I-Green Initiative. These integration need to be catalyzed and supported by targeted component such as government, private sector and society to implement green economy as reforms toward sustainable development.

4. CONCLUSION

Environmental problem happening around the world creates a lot of effects such as climate change, disasters, decreasing of natural resources, and other terrible effects. These problem are spread all over the world indicate the global corporation in solving this problem. I-Green Initiate is one of the solutions to imply the collaboration from three main sector including government, private sector, and society. Government as the policy makers can contribute in making regulation to support private sector to transform to be the green business and provide incentive for society to consume green products. Private sector as the one who contribute such significant amount of carbon emission should put the green vision in its business process in order to minimize the manufacturing effect and produce more green products for society. Society as the consumer should corporate hand in hand to consume green product and imply green consumption in its activity in consuming goods. This integration will conclude all aspect to cooperate in implementing green economy toward sustainable development.

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